

**THE IMPORTANT ROLE OF THE HOUSE-MUSEUM OF OYBEK IN
THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUTH OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE**

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***Abstract.** The article scientifically analyzes the house-museum of Oybek, the brightest star of Uzbek literature, and its importance in the education of youth - the continuers of the Third Renaissance. A visit to the Oybek house-museum became important at one time not only for Uzbeks, but also for foreigners.*

***Keywords:** house, museum, books, articles, paintings, victims of repression, literary exhibition.*

During his lifetime, Oybek became famous among the people not only as a great writer, but also as a great man. Therefore, to use a popular expression, Tashkent residents aged from seven to seventy years, as well as literature lovers from near and far abroad, considered it an honor to come to this house and visit this bright figure of Uzbek literature. Famous writers, translators and literary scholars from cities such as Baku, Alma-Ata and Ashgabat recalled conversations with Oybek in this apartment as unforgettable moments in their lives. Oybek was born on January 10, 1905 in the Gavkush district of Tashkent. This quarter was located in the Khadra district of Tashkent - on the site of the building of the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater. The future writer was born in a low-rise

building in a narrow and winding area, so during his years of study he lived in a dormitory of the Navoi Pedagogical College [1, p. 59]. Having started a family, he lived in rented houses in four districts of Tashkent. Finally, in 1940, when the state distributed land to factory and plant workers, as well as to scientists and cultural figures, he also received a plot of land of 600 square meters. Adiba's wife, Zarifa Saidnosirova, a teacher at the Tashkent Medical Institute, was both the «chief architect» and the «chief foreman» of the construction, and Oybek himself was both the «money maker» with his creative and scientific work and the «fitter» who straightened old crooked nails with a hammer and gave them «new life». On December 30 of that year, they moved into a new house in one fell swoop – their own house.

During the difficult years of construction, not all the buildings were erected, and the roads and sidewalks had not yet acquired a definite appearance. That is why the street was called «Proektnaya». This street is now called «Iftikhor-1». If you walk along this street for three or four minutes, you will reach house 26. On the wall to the left of the main gate there is a memorial plaque stating that the great Uzbek writer Oybek lived in this house from 1940 to 1968. It took Zarifa Saidnosirova more than five years to completely transfer the Oybek archive to the state. The employees of the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, who participated in the preparation for the publication of the 20-volume «Complete Works» of the writer and the creation of the museum exposition, came here almost every day, as if to work. As a result, a group of researchers was formed, which even after 37 years is still considered the «heart» of our museum [2]. All the people who contributed to the creation of the museum became famous literary scholars and famous Oybek scholars. Among them are doctors of philological sciences Naim Karimov, Bakhtiyor Nazarov, Gafar Muminov, Mashkhura Sultanova, Ninel Vladimirova, Rano Ibrogimova, laureates of the Beruni State Prize, academicians and professors, authors of dozens of books and hundreds of articles on Oybek's work. They spent most of their time in

Oybek's workshop, working on the writer's manuscripts, which were carefully preserved thanks to Zarifa Saidnosirova [3, pp. 88-92]. Zarifa Saidnosirova not only collected these manuscripts over many years, but also kept them with great love, and in the mid-70s she began the honorable and difficult task of creating a memorial house-museum of the writer. The scientific and creative team did everything to bring the house-museum to life. This team not only reviewed and systematized the writer's entire archive, but also revived the museum collection, took up exhibition work, and created a literary exhibition based on a thematic exhibition plan.

How long did it take to reconstruct the old building and adapt it for the museum, prepare the equipment, design the exhibition and order the sculpture? The artists who created the exposition were involved in this work. Finally, one of the most joyful and important events in the life of the museum arrived - the opening day of the museum. Zarifa Saidnosirova waited for this day for a long time and with beautiful dreams.

The Oybek House Museum was created in 1985 to commemorate the 80th anniversary of the writer's birth. Everyone who visits the museum will see a bronze statue of Oybek (author I. Klinitsky) in the middle of a cozy garden surrounded by ornamental trees, bushes and flowers. He planted trees and flowers in his small garden. Among the trees he planted are a large, branchy plane tree and a spear-shaped juniper, which decorate the museum's courtyard and delight visitors. Oybek loved to relax and reflect here, among the trees. The museum is located in two buildings built by Oybek himself and is divided into a memorial section, a literary exhibition and a cozy garden. The five-room building, built in 1940-1941, houses an exhibition reflecting the life and creative path of the writer. The literary exhibition is based on Oybek's diaries, notes, letters, photographs, ethnography, examples of fine and applied art, artistic and journalistic works of the writer, as well as the memoirs of contemporaries about Oybek.

This building houses a literary exhibition covering all periods of the writer's life and literary work. The memorial part of the museum, inextricably linked with the literary and historical exhibition, embodies the living spirit and breath of the writer's creative life. After passing through the gate and entering, visitors begin their acquaintance with the exhibition of the Oybek House-Museum in the room on the left, which once served as an aviary.

At the entrance to this part, consisting of 5 rooms, there is a small room on the right side. The exhibition presents exhibits: paintings, documents, objects and works of fine art related to the writer's wife, the daughter of the first Uzbek artist and the first Uzbek chemist Zarifa Saidnosirova, as well as her father, the famous educator and entrepreneur Saidnosir Mirjalilov (1884-1937), a prominent figure in the Uzbek intelligentsia, executed as an «enemy of the people» in 1937. The exhibition located here tells about the diverse activities of this remarkable figure, and the historical elements of the interior tell about the events of 1929-1937, introducing visitors to the incredible and tragic fate of S. Mirjalilov. The breath of a distant and long-gone era is felt in the exhibits presented here.

One of the central places in the hall is occupied by Zarifa Saidnosirova's painting «Tomb of Akhmad Yassawi», created in 1925. The mausoleum, depicted with great skill, is flooded with sunbeams falling from all sides. This real work of art will amaze future generations. This room is also decorated with folk arts and crafts.

After you leave the room, Zarifa Saidnosirova will take you to a room that will introduce you to Oybek's childhood and youth.

This is what Tashkent looked like at the beginning of the 20th century; photographs of the writer of that period; teachers and students of the educational institution where he studied; manuscripts and printed copies of his early poems; Poets and their books that influenced the formation of Oybek's work.

The second hall will introduce you to Oybek's life and work in the 1930s and 1940s. During these years, the writer especially valued the creative sources of

Navoi and Pushkin. He wrote poems and scientific articles dedicated to Navoi; He was the first to translate Pushkin's verse novel «Eugene Onegin» into Uzbek, the language of one of the peoples of Central Asia.

In 1937, he wrote the novel «Blood of Memory». At a time when the novels «Enemies of the People» by Abdulla Kadiri and Chulpon were banned, «Kutlug Kon» inspired, encouraged and guided young Uzbek writers to write novels. The books in different languages presented in the four-sided display case in the center of the room testify to the fact that «Kutlug Kon» is one of the masterpieces of world literature.

From one of the paintings on the wall, the eyes of an Uzbek sniper are looking at you. This color picture was painted by an artist-soldier. When Oybek, as part of the Uzbek government delegation in late 1942 and early 1943, brought gifts and greetings to the Uzbek fighters who were dying and committing suicide on the outskirts of Moscow, this painting was given to him by a remarkable Uzbek youth who «put down» 96 Germans. This soldier, who died without having time to write the number “100” on his sniper rifle, served as the prototype for the character Bektemir in the writer’s novel “The Sun Does Not Darken”. The writer, who spent four months at the front, disturbing his family, returned home in the middle of the night in the last days of March 1943, exhausted, and said: “I will not wake up my children and disturb them,” and slowly knocked on the window next to this photograph. Along with dozens of Russian writers and artists who found refuge in Uzbek lands during the war, including Anna Akhmatova, Alexei Tolstoy, Alexander Deich, Solomon Mikhoels and Vladimir Lugovskoy, he also enjoyed the love and affection of Oybek. During these years, Oybek translated their works into Uzbek. In collaboration with Deich, he wrote a book about Navoi in Russian; L. Batni, who was preparing to write a story about Alisher’s childhood, provided materials about Navoi; Together with Mikhoels he created the opera «Makhmud Torabiy»; the music for this opera was written by the Ukrainian composer Oles

Chishko. The fruits of such creative collaboration spread their wings in this hall as well.

The third hall's exhibition focuses on Navoi. Although Oybek's immortal work about the great poet was written and completed during the war years, it gained international attention and fame in the post-war period. This work, which was awarded a prestigious state award, has been translated into various foreign languages and is of great importance in helping people around the world get to know the great Uzbek writer better. Several articles have been published about Oybek's work and activities. In particular, we recommend that you familiarize yourself with the research of G.K. Masharipova [4, pp. 43-49; 5, 15-17; 6, 7, 4-10-bb; 8, pp. 273-276; 9, pp. 336-338; 10, pp. 242, 11, p. 302].

Unfortunately, the new wave of Stalinist repressions, which began in the early 1950s, again drew Oybek into its clutches. Opponents even try to find political mistakes in the novel «Navoi». This is told in newspaper articles, photographs and documents presented at the exhibition. The ground under the feet of the great writer becomes brighter every day. On one of these painful, agonizing days, he has a stroke. The tongue loses the ability to speak and use hands. During these years, Zarifa Saidnosirova concentrated all her efforts on getting Oybek back on his feet.

Conclusion. Every time we, professors, teachers and students of the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, visit the Oybek House Museum, we acquire a huge store of knowledge, and Zarifa's devotion to Oybek, her patriotism, her importance in raising children serve as a school of education for us, the young. We are grateful to them for this.

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